

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF NON-INVASIVE ANEMIA DETECTION TECHNIQUES: CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Anemia is a nutritional deficiency highly prevalent among under developed and developing nations. Anemia associated with pregnancy poses severe health/ mortality risks to both mother and infant. Early detection of anemia and treatment is the only solution to reduce the mortality risks. In many developing and under developed countries, early detection is challenging due to low reach and higher cost of invasive diagnostics methods. Towards this end, many non-invasive methods have been developed. These methods use various imaging modalities like eye conjunctiva, fingertip, palm, lip mucosa for detection of anemia. These methods can be briefly categorized to conventional and deep learning methods. Though many techniques have been developed in both categories, the area of non-invasive detection still presents many issues in terms of accuracy, false positives etc. Various challenges in image acquisition, feature engineering, classifier design and optimization etc, need to be addressed to achieve higher accuracy and lower false positives. This work does a critical analysis of existing noninvasive techniques for detection and categorization of anemia. Analysis is done in three categories of image acquisition, feature engineering and classification. The aim is to identify the research gaps and present a solution architecture to address those gaps.

Keywords: *Anemia; NonInvasive Methods; Machine Learning; Deep Learning; Palpebral Conjunctiva; Fingernail Bed Analysis;*

1 INTRODUCTION

Anemia is a most common nutritional deficiency prevalent largely in developing and under developed countries. Though it can be prevented easily, the effect of it severe when not treated in time for the case of pregnant women. Multi factors like reduced food intake, lack of nutritional diet, altered metabolism, susceptibility to infectious diseases like hookworm infestations etc. can trigger anemia and make it severe during pregnancy. In absence of timely treatment, it becomes an important cause for maternal and paternal mortality [1]. Early diagnosis is an important factor influencing the preventive care and early treatment. Anemia is characterized by lower levels of hemoglobin in the blood. As per World Health Organization (WHO) criteria hemoglobin (Hgb) level below 11 g/dL is defined as anemia for pregnant women [2]. The standard clinical method for anemia diagnosis is

measurement of hemoglobin level from the blood samples. This invasive procedure is uncomfortable, costly, time consuming and infeasible (when repeated measurements are needed). It is also prone to spread of infections in places where health care facilities are unhygienic. Thus, a highly reliable non-invasive method for anemia detection and characterization was needed. In this background, many non-invasive techniques have been developed. The techniques are based on the visual indication of progression in pallor of skin. The progression can be noticed in areas where skin is thin, such as the eye conjunctiva, lip mucosa, tongue, fingertip nail and oral mucosa. Various techniques have been proposed making use of these modalities. The images obtained from these modalities were processed to detect and characterize anemia. These techniques can be broadly classified to conventional and deep learning techniques. Conventional techniques extract handcraft features from the images and train traditional machine learning classifiers like Support

Vector Machine (SVM), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Random Forest (RF), Decision Trees etc., in standalone mode or ensemble mode to detect and categorize anemia.

The problem with conventional techniques is that detection performance depends on the modality used and the choice of handcraft features. Deep learning techniques learn intricate features using sequence of convolution and pooling without the need for handcraft features. They provide higher accuracy compared to conventional classifier but the accuracy depends on quality of training and learning bias.

Despite the promise of non-invasive techniques, several critical challenges hinder their widespread adoption and clinical utility. First, image acquisition remains a bottleneck, as variations in ambient lighting, device specifications, and user handling significantly affect image quality and reliability. Most current solutions lack adaptive mechanisms to assess or correct image suitability in real time. Second, the extracted features often fail to generalize across populations due to insufficient consideration of demographic factors such as age, skin tone, ethnicity, and comorbid conditions. Third, a majority of the models—especially those using deep learning—are trained on small, homogeneous datasets, which introduces learning bias and restricts cross-domain generalizability. Lastly, many of the proposed methods are unimodal, relying on a single source of input (e.g., conjunctiva or fingertip), thereby increasing susceptibility to noise and reducing diagnostic confidence. Addressing these issues requires a multi-dimensional approach that integrates robust image preprocessing, context-aware feature engineering, demographic adaptation, and multimodal data fusion. In this context, multimodal systems, which combine features from multiple anatomical sites or integrate clinical metadata with visual inputs, have shown promise in enhancing libraries and research databases. The number of publications was then reduced in accordance with inclusion and exclusion criteria.

2.1 Search Process and Source of Information

To identify the studies focusing on machine learning and deep learning techniques applied to non-invasive anemia detection, an extensive search was done across major research databases. In order

model robustness and reducing false positives. Furthermore, **cross-modal** learning and transformer-based architectures offer new opportunities for improving feature representation and decision-making across diverse input modalities.

This paper presents a comprehensive survey and critical evaluation of the current state-of-the-art in non-invasive anemia detection. The survey is structured around three functional components—image acquisition, feature engineering, and classification—and further categorizes methods based on the modality of input data (unimodal vs. multimodal). Through this systematic review, the study identifies key limitations in existing approaches and articulates open research challenges. In response, a prospective solution architecture is proposed, incorporating best practices and novel strategies to address identified gaps, including image quality validation, cross-domain learning, and multi-source feature fusion.

The ultimate objective of this work is to guide the development of next-generation non-invasive anemia screening systems that are accurate, scalable, demographically inclusive, and suitable for deployment in real-world, resource-constrained environments.

2. METHODOLOGY

To conduct the systematic review outlined in this work, a review procedure has been developed. The review protocol's goal is to regulate the review process, reduce the likelihood of publication bias and offer a thorough grasp of the field's research trends, difficulties, and developments. A broad search of academic literature was carried out to find the relevant research publications using multiple digital

to focus on recent developments, the search window was restricted to the years 2015–2024.

2.2 Criteria for Inclusion and Exclusion

The following inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to choose the most relevant research for this survey once relevant papers were retrieved from the databases. Figure 1 illustrates the systematic study selection process followed in this

review. The databases and digital libraries listed below were utilized:

- IEEE Xplore: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org>
- Springer: <https://link.springer.com>
- ScienceDirect: <https://sciencedirect.com>
- The ACM Digital Library: <https://dl.acm.org>.
- Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com>
- PubMed: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- Works that used deep learning or machine learning techniques.
- Research that concentrates on the extraction of features based on images from anatomical areas such as the palm, fingernail, fingertip, or eye conjunctiva.
- Research that addressed or helped resolve one or more of the research questions that were posed.

2.3 Criteria for Inclusion

- English-language articles.
- Research on the detection of anemia or non-invasive hemoglobin estimation.

2.4 Criteria for Exclusion

- Articles unrelated to hemoglobin estimation or anemia detection.
- Articles that only discussed invasive method of diagnostic procedures.
- Articles without performance evaluation or experimental validation.

Figure 1 Systematic review study selection process

Figure 2 Survey taxonomy

3. RELATED WORKS

The taxonomy of the survey is given in Figure 2. Based on functional components, survey is conducted in three areas of acquisition, feature engineering and classification. In classification area, conventional and deep learning techniques are surveyed. Based on input modalities, the survey is conducted in two areas of unimodal and multimodal approaches.

3.1 Acquisition

Impact of ambient light is a major problem in image acquisition for anemia detection. Asare et al [3] turned of the camera's spotlights to eliminate impact of ambient light and also extracted the conjunctiva region from acquired images using edge based outlining the eye region. But the method used for conjunctiva region extraction used many fixed thresholds and not generic to all age groups. Bauskar et al [4] slightly pulled the lower eyelid to acquire magnified eye conjunctiva image. Authors manually avoided excessive bright or dark images. These images affected the accuracy. Jain et al [5] followed the same approach and filtered excessive bright or dark images. But the selection was manual. Suner et al [6] relied on obtaining eye

conjunctive images only in ambient indoor light. By this way influence of glare was minimized. Mannino et al [7] proposed a quality control algorithm to remove camera flash reflections or leukonychia from affecting Hgb measurements made from finger nail image. Color values outside the average range are excluded by the quality control algorithm and through this way authors found a significant improvement of 76% in the Hgb measurements. But the method was not tested for images acquired from different devices under different lighting environments. Anggraeni et al [8] implemented a method to capture palpebral image at a closer distance of 30-40 cm in ambient lighting condition to reduce the influence of glare in the image. Jayakody et al [9] experimented with color of light, kind of light emitting device and distance between finger nail to lighting system to decide the best values for noise free image capture. Though the author found that white LED performs better, author did not provide any model for distance and light intensity to be used for noise free image capture. Kumar et al [10] captured PPG signals at various wavelength from LED reflections over fingertip to solve the problem of noise during data acquisition for Hgb calculation. But the setup requires costly spectroscopy device with multiple tuning parameters which makes it difficult to operate and needs trained personal.

Table 1 Analysis on existing Image Acquisition methods

Authors	Work Done	Disadvantage	Summary
Asare et al [3]	Switched camera's spotlight to acquire conjunctiva image. Applied edge detection method to extract ROI	Approach was not generic and lacked image suitability analysis before Hgb estimation	Automatic method for image capture with image suitability analysis for Hgb estimation which can provide suggestions to user and improve the image acquisition process has not been considered in previous works
Bauskar et al [4], Jain et al [5], Ghosal et al [13]	Manual filtering of excessive bright or dark images	Lacked automatic suitability analysis of image	
Suner et al [6], Donmez et al [14], Rojas et al [15]	Avoided influence of glare by selecting indoor environment and lighting conditions	Approach was not generic	
Mannino et al [7]	Quality control algorithm to remove camera flash reflections affecting finger nail capture. The algorithm excluded colour values outside average range.	Approach was not tested for different devices under different lighting environments	
Anggraeni et al [8]	Controlled distance to image capture manually to get good quality palpebral image.	Approach was manual and not generic for variance in lighting environments.	
Kumar et al [10]	Controlled spectrographic parameters to obtain good quality images	Costly setup and required trained personal to operate.	
Peksi et al [11]	Obtained palm and finger nail images in absence of direct sunlight by controlling the distance to capture manually.	Device dependent and approach is not generic	
Haggenmüller et al [12]	Manual selection of ROI regions in finger nail image	Approach requires trained personal to operate	

Peksi et al [11] acquired palm and finger nail images in absence of direct sunlight to avoid the impact of ambient light. In addition, author fixed the distance between camera to palm and nail through trial and error to obtain better quality images. But the approach is not generic and not applicable for all cameras. Haggenmüller et al [12] selected the ROI regions in finger nail manually to eliminate the influence of dirt and other light introduced noise factors. But the approach is

cumbersome and there is no image pre-analysis to decide suitability of the image for Hgb calculation. Ghosal et al [13] manually filtered conjunctival images before they were used for Hgb calculation. They checked if conjunctival image is properly focused before taking it for further processing.

Donmez et al [14] used a frame structure to capture lip moucas region alone in indoor environment with camera lighting. By this way

author avoided light interference and also made segmentation easier. But mobility becomes difficult with this method. Rojas et al [15] used fluorescent light bulbs in indoor environment to capture the eye conjunctiva image. In addition, authors controlled shutter speed and distance to object to obtain good quality image for Hgb estimation. The summary of the approaches is presented in Table 1. The existing methods to obtain good quality images for Hgb estimation involves controlling the image capture environment, controlling the photographic variables, manual elimination of unsuitable images, relying on multiple image captures etc. Automatic method for image capture with image suitability analysis for Hgb estimation which can provide suggestions to user and improve the image acquisition process has not been considered in previous works.

3.2 Feature engineering

Asare et al [3] extracted mean of red, green and blue color pixel values in the conjunctiva region and calculated Hgb fitting these values in a formula. The formulas were obtained using logistic regression. But in absence of large samples, the validity of model cannot be ascertained. Bauskaret al [4] extracted the red and green component of eye conjunctiva image and used it calculate Hgb value. Their study was based on higher Pearson correlation value between red component of eye conjunctiva to Hgb values concluded by Dimauro et al [16]. Similarly, Jain et al [5] used redcolor component to estimate Hgb but they extracted the feature only from the ROI region of conjunctiva instead of entire conjunctiva image.

Anggraeni et al [8] extracted mean red pixel intensity from eye conjunctiva region and used it to calculate Hgb value. Authors used linear regression without any bias variables to adapt the model to different data sources. The study was conducted only with 20 pregnant woman and linear regression modeling with limited dataset could be biased. Suner et al [6] extracted 26 different parameters representing average brightness of the image, average value of red image component, flash activation and entropy of the image. Authors used the parameters to estimate Hgb with regression analysis. Though authors demonstrated significant correlation between the predicted

hemoglobin level and clinically measured hemoglobin level, the test was conducted only on limited test set. Further images used for training and testing are from single source, which leads to learning bias. Chakraborty et al [9] extracted a set of 13 attenuation and ratio-of-ratio features, derived using the peak and trough information extracted from the finger PPG signals. These features for used for anemia classification. Kumar et al [11] extracted 11 incident intensity features from fingertip PPG signals and classified to Hgb level using regression. Though this method was able to detect hemoglobin level as low as 1.6 g/dL, authors did not experiment sensitivity for different age groups.

Peksi et al [18] extracted color features from nail and palm images. Haggemüller et al [19] used color features of fingernail bed images to detect hemoglobin level. The performance of the approach was tested with different socio-economic, ethnic, demographic and cultural composition in rural Bihar, India. The accuracy was very low and it could not be used as reliable screening mechanism. Hasan et al [21] extracted mean RGB pixel intensities from each frame of finger nail video (with 300 frames). These values are aggregated as features and used for Hgb estimation. Similar to Hasan et al [19], Ahsan et al [23] extracted mean RGB pixel intensities from each frame of finger nail video and aggregated it as features. But they removed outlier frames using singular value decomposition before aggregating as features. Pintaviroojet al [25] measured absorption coefficients of blood using various electromagnetic wavelengths. These coefficients are then applied on modified Beer–Lambert law to estimate Hgb. But this approach requires laboratory environment. Lakshmi et al [27] extracted principal component analysis (PCA) features from the PPG signals and used it for Hgb estimation.

Shao et al [28] extracted absorption spectroscopy spectra from finger tips. From these spectra, amplitude points are extracted. Multilinear regression analysis is applied with the amplitude points to estimate Hgb. Okazaki et al [30] extracted the depth and diameter of venous blood vessel image obtained using complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) camera with LED light. Hgb is estimated from the depth and diameter features using regression.

Table 2 Analysis On Existing Feature Engineering Methods

Input	Feature	Authors	Gap
Eye conjunctiva	Colour features(Mean of red, green and blue colour pixel values) are fit using regression to estimate Hgb	Asare et al [3], Ghosal et al [13], Espinoza et al [20], Sevani et al [22] Bauskar et al [4] Zhao et al [33] Wemyss et al [35] Tamir et al [41] Kasiviswanathan et al [44]	In absence of large samples, the validity of model cannot be ascertained. Also, the model is made generic without accommodating factors like age, ethnicity factors. Most of the regression models are linear. Fitting non linear and fuzzy models can be explored.
	Mean red pixel intensity	Anggraeni et al [8] Jain et al [5] Chen et al [32] Collings et al [39]	
Finger tip	Attenuation features, PCA features, wavelet features from PPG signals are fit into regression model to estimate Hgb	Chakraborty et al [9] Kumar et al [11] Lakshmi et al [27] Peng et al [36] Acharya et al [37]	
	Color features from finger nail bed images	Haggenmüller et al [19] Hasan et al [21]	
	absorption spectroscopy spectra coefficients	Pintavirooj et al [25] Shaoo et al [28] Okazaki et al [30] Fan et al [38]	
Palm	Color features	Appiahene et al [5] Peksi et al [18]	

Chen et al [32] extracted red component from the conjunctiva and fitting Kalman curve with non linear penalty regression to estimate Hgb value. Zhao et al [33] used the same method of Suner et al [6] but to improve accuracy, they extracted features from both left and right eye and ensemble the results. Wemyss et al [35] extracted five color features of erythema index, *r* chromaticity, *-g* chromaticity, *a** chromaticity, *b** chromaticity from the palpebral conjunctiva

image and used it for anemia classification. Peng et al [36] extracted wavelet features from eight channel PPG signals and from these features, best set of features are selected using Support Vector Regression-Recursive Feature Elimination (SVR-RFE) algorithm. Acharya et al [37] extracted peak and trough from 4 channel PPG signal and created an attenuated feature vector for detecting Hgb level. Fan et al [38] extracted absorption coefficient from 5 LED wavelength signals

emanating from finger tip and fitted a multi linear regression model to predict Hgb. But this method was tested only on 24 subjects and needs a laboratory setup for signal acquisition.

Collings et al [39] extracted brightness of red and green channel from conjunctiva image and fitted into the equation proposed by Yamamoto et al [40] to estimate erythema index (EI) which has higher correlation to Hgb. Though the method achieved a sensitivity and specificity of 69% and 72%, it was tested only against limited dataset and from single source.

Tamir et al [41] extracted mean red and green color intensity from conjunctiva region. They then calculated the mean difference between the two intensities and thresholded to classify anemia. Kim et al [43] used a combination of reflectance spectrometry and stochastic simulation of photon movement in eyelid tissue for estimating Hgb. Though the method achieved an RMSE of 1.64 g/dL, it operated in limited range of 8.1 to 16.7 g/dL. Also the method was tested only with 30 cases. Kasiviswanathan et al [44] extracted color features and combined with information of height, age, sex and weight. Ridge regression is fit on these features to estimate Hgb level. Though the authors achieved RMSE of 1.72 g/dl, the tests were conducted with small dataset and from single source.

The summary of the feature engineering methods for various modalities are given in Table 2. The validity of more regression models fitting the features extracted from input to Hgb needs to be tested for large samples, different demographics and ethnicities. Most Hgb models did not consider factors like age, sex etc and the influence of these factors on Hgb estimation in various ranges needs to be explored.

3.3 Classification

3.3.1 Conventional classification methods

Jain et al [4] used Artificial neural networks (ANN) to classify the features extracted from eye conjunctiva images to two class of anemia or not anemia. Authors used image augmentation to increase training image volume and hyper parameter tuning to maximize the performance of ANN. Though authors claimed an accuracy of 97%, the performance was tested for limited test set. False positives were not tested.

Appiahene et al [5] experimented with different machine learning models with features extracted from palm images. They achieved an accuracy of 96%. Data augmentation was used to increase training set volume. Bias removal in dataset is not considered and false positives were not measured. Chakraborty et al [9] classified PPG features to three anemic classes of healthy, anemia and severe anemic using ensemble of machine learning classifiers. False positives are higher in this method.

Peksi et al [18] used Naïve Bayes algorithm to classify color features extracted from palm to predict anemia. Though the method was able to achieve 87% accuracy, it is highly dependent on light intensity. Also, the dataset was from single source. Hasan et al [21] used ANN to predict Hgb level from the RGB features for finger nail video. Though authors found that there was a correlation of 0.93 between the model and gold standard hemoglobin levels in their sample of patients aged 20 to 56 years, the testing was conducted with limited dataset and dataset was from single source. Sevani et al [22] used K-means algorithm to cluster RGB intensity features from conjunctival image to classify anemia. Though the method achieved an accuracy of 90%, it was tested with limited dataset and dataset characteristics are unknown. Instead of K-means, Ahsan et al [23] experimented with decision tree, SVM and naïve Bayes algorithm to classify RGB features extracted from finger nail videos. But they were able to obtain only a maximum accuracy of 48.8%. Banerjee et al [24] used multilayer ANN to process the light spectrum reflection from fingertip to estimate Hgb. Though this method achieved higher accuracy, it can be used only in lab environment as it is not robust to ambient light noises.

Fredriksson et al [26] processed diffuse reflectance spectroscopy spectra from skin dermis using ANN to estimate Hgb. Though authors found higher correlation of spectra to Hgb, this method can only be used in laboratory environment. Lakshmi et al [27] used ANN to process the PCA components and predict Hgb. Testing was not conducted with pediatric patients, accurately ill patient, pregnant population and surgical patients. Dimauro extracted RGB and HSV features from the eye conjunctiva region and classified it using RUSBoost classifier to detect anemia. Use of RUSBoost solves the class imbalance problem. The method had accuracy of about 88%, but it needs to be tested against different demographics. Wemyss et

al [35] classified color features extracted from conjunctiva into anemic class using two classifiers: linear regression and NaïveBayes classifier. Though the method was able to achieve sensitivity of 92.9% and a specificity of 89.7%, it was tested only on single population and results against various demographics was not explored.

Peng et al [36] used extreme learning machine (ELM) to classify wavelet features extracted from PPG signals to Hgb levels. The method was able to achieve an RMSE of 1.72 g/dL when tested across 249 clinical data points. But all the data are from single source and approach lacked testing across various demographics. Acharya et al [37] used a two layer stacked regression model to predict Hgb values from the attenuated feature vector extracted from PPG signals. At first level, authors experimented with LASSO, Ridge, Elastic net and Ada boost. At the second level, SVM regressor was used. Though the method achieved RMSE of 1.353 g/dL, it was tested for small Hgb range of 7g/dL to 11g/dL. Also, the method was not tested for different demographics and ethnics. Fuadah et al [45] extracted first order statistical features from eye conjunctiva image and classified the features using KNN classifier to anemic class. The method was able to achieve an accuracy of 71.25%. But the dataset size is limited and from single source.

Dejene et al [48] experimented with three machine learning models of random forest, extreme gradient boosting, and cat boost for classifying textual features to anemia. Though authors achieved an accuracy above 90%, the test was conducted on single source data. Ghosh et al [49] used ANN to classify blood drop images to anemic class. The color information features extracted from blood drop images is classified by 5 layer neural network. Though the solution achieved sensitivity of 95.5% and specificity of 52%, it was tested with only 86 samples and the results depend on blood drop image acquisition procedure. Chen et al [52] used SVM and ANN classifier to classify anemia class from the color/entropy features extracted from conjunctiva image. Though ANN achieved 62% sensitivity and 90% specificity, the method was tested only with 50 images.

3.3.2 Deep learning methods

Mitani et al [3] used Inception V4 deep learning architecture to classify eye fundus images to two classes of anemia or not anemia. Testing

against UK Biobank dataset the solution was able to achieve about 78% accuracy. The method was based on observation that anemia of sufficient severity, develops some characteristics signs in eye fundus. Authors did not threshold the characteristics signs leading to misinterpretation. As the result, false positives are higher in this method. Jayakody et al [10] classified the finger tip image to anemic level using convolutional neural network (CNN). Though the root mean square value between the predicted value and clinical measurement value is 0.43%, the method lacked sensitivity and specificity measurements. Also, the nature of dataset for experimentation is unknown. Magdalena et al [12] used CNN to classify eye conjunctiva image to two classes of anemia and normal. The dataset for experimentation was from single source and this can create bias. Das et al [28] applied a combination of convolutional neural network (CNN) and vision transformer (VIT) over the segmented eyelid images to predict Hgb level. The method has lower accuracy in the extreme upper (>16 g/dL) and lower (< 8 g/dL) hemoglobin values. Also, the outliers are higher than 8%. Zhang et al [34] extracted face from videos and experimented with deep learning methods for classifying anemia. They experimented with five deep learning models of ResNet50, MobileNet, InceptionV3, EfficientNetB0, and DenseNet121. Though the authors achieved above 80% accuracy, the suitability of method in various demographics and lighting conditions was not explored.

Muljono et al [42] classified eye conjunctiva image using hybrid deep learning model combining SVM with MobileNetV2 deep learning model. Though the method was able to achieve an accuracy of 93%, it was tested only with 121 images from single source. Rivero-Palacio et al [46] used YOLO v5 deep learning model to classify ocular conjunctiva image to anemic class. Though the method was able to achieve a sensitivity of 0,71 and a specificity of 0.89, it was tested only for smaller dataset of children below 5 years old. . Asare et al [47] used CNN for classifying anemia using eye conjunctiva, palm and fingernail. CNN was trained with AlexNet and the stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimization. CNN was able to achieve an accuracy of above 90% for all the image modes and it performed better compared to conventional classifiers. But the test was limited to subjects with less than 5 years. Magdalena et al [50] used CNN to classify palpebral conjunctiva images to anemia

class. Though the method was able to achieve above 90% accuracy, the dataset was from single source. Testing across different demographics were not explored. Mitani et al [51] used Inception V4 deep learning model to classify retinal fundus images to anemic class. Though this method has mean absolute error of 0.73, the test dataset has

more than 91% white ethnicity. Chen et al [53] used MobileNet V3 deep neural network model to predict Hb concentration from the conjunctiva image. Though the method had mean absolute error of 1.521, it was tested only with limited dataset. Also, the dataset was from single source.

Table 3 Problems in existing classification techniques

Problem	Description
Limited dataset	Most of the conventional and deep learning models were tested on limited dataset from single source. Demographic and ethnic diversities were not considered in most of the testing dataset.
Higher accuracy only in limited range of for small Hgb range of 7g/dL to 11g/dL	Most works achieved higher accuracy of above 90% only in limited range of 7g/dL to 11g/dL. Hyper parameter tuning and ensembling classifiers to increase the operating range was not explored in most of the works
Learning bias	Most methods were trained on dataset obtained from single source. Cross source learning was not explored in existing works

Figure 3 Cross source learning mechanism (Source: Jingjing et al [58])

The summary of the problems in existing classification techniques are presented in Table 3. Three important problems in existing classification techniques are: limited dataset, accuracy in limited

range and learning bias. Most approaches are trained with limited dataset. For deep learning approaches, many works used data augmentation techniques to increase the data volume, but without

diversity in dataset, it only added to learning bias. Cross source learning is a method that can be used to solve this problem of learning bias and limited dataset. A cross-source learning setup is presented in Figure 3. The same image like eye conjunctiva can be acquired in different ways like spectral, RGB etc and features can be first learning separately and then in mutual manner to obtain fused features with higher discriminating ability to classify anemia.

3.3.3 Modality

Most of the existing approaches discussed so far were unimodal. They used either one of input modality of eye conjunctiva, palm, fingertip. Relying on single modality results in higher probability of false probabilities and lower accuracy. Multi modal approach is a solution to this problem. Multi modal approaches combines multiple modalities. Kasiviswanathan et al [44] combined meta data information like age, height, weight of subject along with eye conjunctiva image to predict Hgb level. Ramzan et al [54] used palm image along with corpuscular concentration levels with deep learning attention model to predict anemia. Features of palm and corpuscular concentration are fused and used for classification. This approach of fusing features before classification is referred as early or feature fusion.

Mitani et al [51] proposed a early fusion approach combining clinical features with deep learning features from retinal fundus image to create hybrid feature and classified the hybrid feature to anemic class. Ramzan et al [55] fused features extracted from electronic health records with features extracted from eye conjunctiva images using Reverse Convolution Block Attention Mechanism. The fused features are classified to anemic class. The accuracy increased to 95% with fused features. Though testing with various demographics and ethnics is absent, the approach was promising as it yielded superior performance

compared to image only and text only based anemia classification.

Khan et al [56] fused age, gender with deep learning features extracted from retinal fundus images using Inception V4 deep learning model. Though this model achieved 98% accuracy, median age of subjects was 50 years. Kumar et al [57] proposed a cross-modal transformer-based fusion approach for multimodal clinical data analysis using medical images and clinical data. Images are converted to visual tokens using image embedding layer. Clinical data are converted to text tokens using a clinical embedding layer. Holistic representation of image and text is learnt using a cross-modal transformer module. Though this approach was tested for lung disease tuberculosis, the core idea of cross modal transformer fusion can be extended for multiple image modality (eye conjunctiva, fingertip, palm, lip mucosa) to improve the accuracy and reduce false positives.

4. OPEN ISSUES

From the survey following open issues can be identified. The prospective solutions to the problems in areas of image acquisition, feature engineering, classification and modality are summarized in Figure 5.

4.1 Resiliency to environment:

Lighting is the major factor impacting the accuracy of anemia detection. Without adjustment of the lighting illumination and white balance, the image acquisition process becomes faulty and this in turn reduces the accuracy. Approaches using specialized hardware to control the external lighting condition are not feasible and thus software based autocorrection facility suited for smartphone environment is necessary. Existing approaches have not considered this problem.

Figure 4 Cross modal transformer approach (Source: Kumar et al [57])

Figure 5 Prospective Solution Suggestion

4.2 Multimodality:

False positives are higher in existing approaches due to environmental noises and feature engineering techniques. There is no correlation analysis between the feature dimensions and anemia classes. The problem of higher false positives can be solved by combining multimodality either in early or late fusion mode. Only very few works have considered multimodal approach for anemia detection. Those works too are based on late fusion. Cross modality learning to enhance the features and using the best set of features for anemia classification have been never considered in existing works. A correlation model based on multi-modality information from eye conjunctiva image, fingertip, palm to the hemoglobin level is lacking and this is necessary for anemia severity analysis.

4.3 Learning bias:

Most of the approaches used data from single source and dataset size is also limited. Table 5 provides the details of dataset used in some of the existing works.

From the Table 4, it can be seen that most methods were tested with limited dataset size with uneven distribution of anemia to non-anemia. Also most datasets are not public. They also did not consider wide demographics like that of Massey score. Images obtained from different acquisition devices were not considered. The sampling population belonged to same ethnic group. The dataset used for testing were limited. These factors create learning bias and affects the reliability of the prediction systems. These problems can be solved by following diversification in image acquisition, sampling across multiple ethnic groups in different age categories.

5. PROBLEM STATEMENT

This study identifies following problems in existing solutions based on the survey.

5.1 Environmental resiliency

Despite advances in non-invasive anemia detection methods using smartphone cameras, the accuracy of hemoglobin estimation remains highly sensitive to environmental conditions such as

ambient lighting, device variability, and camera flash artifacts. Most existing solutions either rely on manual controls or laboratory-grade equipment, making them unsuitable for field use, especially in resource-limited settings. There is a pressing need for an automated, software-based solution capable of assessing image quality in real-time and performing environmental corrections to enable consistent and accurate anemia screening across diverse usage contexts.

5.2 Multimodal integration

The majority of current non-invasive anemia detection systems employ unimodal approaches—typically using images of the eye conjunctiva or fingertip—leading to high false positive rates and poor generalization. These systems fail to capture the full spectrum of physiological indicators necessary for reliable hemoglobin estimation. A robust multimodal framework that integrates complementary anatomical cues has the potential to enhance detection accuracy, reduce false positives, and enable classification across a wider range of hemoglobin values. However, effective fusion strategies for such multimodal data are still underexplored.

5.3 Personalization

Existing models for non-invasive anemia detection often ignore important demographic and physiological variables such as age, gender, ethnicity, and baseline health status. This oversight results in biased predictions and reduced applicability in diverse populations. Since hemoglobin levels and pallor indicators can vary significantly across different demographic groups, there is a critical need for models that incorporate such contextual metadata to support more accurate, equitable, and personalized anemia diagnosis and severity assessment.

5.4 Learning bias

Non-invasive anemia detection systems are frequently trained and validated on limited, single-source datasets with narrow demographic scope. This leads to learning bias, poor model generalization, and overfitting to specific conditions or populations. The lack of public, diverse, and standardized datasets exacerbates this issue. To build scalable and generalizable AI models, there is an urgent requirement for

strategies such as cross-source learning, domain adaptation, and dataset diversification across age, ethnicity, and imaging devices.

5.5 Cross modality learning

Traditional multimodal fusion strategies—such as early or late feature fusion—used in anemia detection often fall short in capturing complex interdependencies between modalities. Recently, cross-modal transformer models have demonstrated superior performance in tasks involving heterogeneous data sources by learning holistic, contextual representations. However, their application to non-invasive anemia detection, especially using anatomical images combined with clinical metadata, remains largely unexplored. Investigating this approach could significantly enhance both the accuracy and interpretability of multimodal anemia detection systems.

Based on these problems, following research questions are framed

1. How can real-time image quality assessment and environmental correction algorithms be developed to improve the robustness of anemia detection under diverse lighting conditions using standard smartphone cameras?
2. Can a unified multimodal deep learning framework combining features from eye conjunctiva, fingertip, palm, and lip mucosa significantly reduce false positives and improve classification accuracy across varied hemoglobin ranges?
3. What is the impact of incorporating demographic and physiological metadata (e.g., age, gender, ethnicity, health status) into multimodal models for personalized anemia severity estimation?
4. How can cross-source learning techniques be applied to reduce learning bias and improve generalizability of non-invasive anemia detection models across datasets with different acquisition devices and populations?
5. To what extent can cross-modal transformer architectures enhance feature representation and decision-making in non-invasive anemia screening compared to traditional early/late fusion methods?

Table 4 Dataset Used In Experimentations

Author	Dataset	Gap
Asare et al [3]	710 participants in age group of 6 to 59 months	Dataset not public. Data from same ethnic group
Dimauro et al [31]	Eyes-defy-anemia dataset with 211 participants with age group of 19 to 75 years.	Though dataset is public it is mostly Italian subjects and very few Indian subjects. Only 42 subjects are anemia thus a uneven data distribution.
Jain et al [5]	Total 99 eye conjunctiva images with 48 anemic	Dataset is not public
Suner et al [6]	Total of 344 subjects in age group of 19 to 96 years. Wide demography was considered in Massey score of 1 to 9.	Dataset is not public
Appiahene et al [5] Peksi et al [18]	Finger nail images of 20 subjects	Most works on finger nail and palm were tested with limited dataset of less than 50, and dataset is not public.
Acharya et al [37]	PPG data of 1583 woman in child bearing age	Dataset is not public.
Kasiviswanathan et al [44]	A total of 135 subjects with 44 anaemic in age group of 18 to 73.	Dataset is not public

Figure 6 Prospective Solution Architecture

6 SOLUTION

Based on the open issues identified, a prospective solution architecture is framed. The architecture is given in Figure 6.

Multi modal inputs collected from multiple cues of eye conjunctiva image, fingertip, palm, lip mucosa are jointly used for anemia classification and severity estimation in this work. The multi modal inputs are processed by various image processing techniques to remove visual artifacts introduced in data acquisition due to factors like light intensity, movements etc. The multi modal inputs are then processed to extract features using cross modal transfer learning (Figure 4) approaches to extract highly relevant features from the inputs. Deep learning classifiers can be used to process the features and classify them to two class of anemia and healthy. A multi-modality correlation model can be developed correlating multimodal features to anemia severity levels. Using the model, the severity of anemia can be estimated.

7 CONCLUSION

This work presented a critical analysis of existing noninvasive anemia detection and categorization techniques. Open issues were identified in three areas of environmental resiliency, multimodality and learning bias. A prospective solution architecture with the techniques to be applied to address the research gaps was detailed. The implementation and benchmarking against different datasets in in scope of future work.

This comprehensive survey critically examined the landscape of non-invasive techniques developed for anemia detection and categorization. Given the high prevalence of anemia in developing and underdeveloped regions—and the limitations posed by invasive diagnostic procedures—the demand for accessible, accurate, and non-invasive solutions is growing rapidly. This paper systematically analyzed the evolution and current state of such solutions across four pivotal dimensions: image acquisition, feature engineering, classification strategies, and modality integration.

In the area of image acquisition, it was evident that many existing methods lack environmental adaptability. Techniques are often highly sensitive to ambient lighting, camera specifications, and manual procedures, resulting in inconsistent image

quality and ultimately impacting hemoglobin (Hgb) estimation accuracy. Furthermore, most acquisition approaches are device-dependent, require skilled operation, or depend on subjective manual filtering—making them unsuitable for scalable and user-friendly deployment, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Feature engineering techniques have traditionally relied on hand-crafted features such as mean RGB intensities and attenuation measures derived from specific anatomical sites like the conjunctiva, fingertip, and palm. However, the validity and robustness of these models are questionable due to the lack of large, diverse, and demographically balanced datasets. Moreover, simplistic linear regression models dominate the field, despite evidence suggesting that more complex, nonlinear or fuzzy models could better capture the nuanced relationships between features and hemoglobin levels.

From a classification standpoint, both conventional machine learning and deep learning methods have been deployed, with deep learning approaches offering promising improvements in accuracy and automation. Nevertheless, the majority of these models suffer from overfitting and learning bias due to limited and non-representative datasets. Few studies have adequately explored cross-source or cross-domain generalization, and very few have addressed the critical need to balance sensitivity and specificity across a broad Hgb range, particularly in borderline or severe anemia cases.

A major limitation found across most existing studies is the unimodal nature of input data. By relying solely on a single modality—be it eye conjunctiva, fingertip, or palm—these systems are inherently susceptible to noise and variability. Multimodal approaches, while still in their infancy in this domain, offer a more resilient path forward. When appropriately fused—whether via early, late, or cross-modal transformer-based methods—multi-source inputs can significantly enhance robustness, reduce false positives, and improve severity-level classification.

The survey also identified several open issues, including the lack of public and demographically

varied datasets, absence of standardized image acquisition protocols, and insufficient correlation modeling between multimodal features and hemoglobin levels. To address these challenges, the paper proposed a prospective solution architecture that incorporates:

- Robust and automated preprocessing to handle environmental variability;
- Cross-modal feature extraction to leverage information from multiple anatomical cues;
- Deep learning classifiers fine-tuned with hyperparameter optimization and cross-domain training strategies; and
- A severity estimation model trained on multimodal data with demographic diversity.

This architecture aims not just at binary classification (anemia vs. healthy) but also at estimating the severity of anemia, enabling it to serve as a more comprehensive and clinically relevant decision-support tool.

In conclusion, while significant progress has been made in the domain of non-invasive anemia detection, the field remains constrained by methodological fragmentation, limited datasets, and narrow performance scopes. The future of this domain lies in holistic, multimodal, and scalable systems underpinned by robust AI models trained on diverse and representative datasets. Future work will focus on implementing and empirically validating the proposed architecture, establishing standardized evaluation protocols, and developing open-access datasets to foster collaborative advancement in this crucial area of healthcare technology.

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